

KAZAKH DIASPORA IS AN INSEPARABLE PART OF KAZAKH NATION*Sovetkhan Zh.,**The student of ACa-21-10, AUPET***Baidildina Fellan S.***Supervisor**PhD (AUPET)***Abstract**

The article is considered the history of the formation and development of Kazakh diaspora. The work is analyzed the process of the formation and development of Kazakh diaspora, taking into account their objective and subjective factors, socio-economic, political and cultural features of past and nowadays based on the analysis of historians' scientific works and interviewing.

Also the policy of Kazakhstan is considered by repatriation of ethnic Kazakhs to their historical homeland.

Keywords: Diaspora, Kazakh diaspora, migration, immigration, ethnic identity.

With the independence of Kazakhstan, one of the most important problems, which has always been in the center of the country's leadership attention, was the establishment of close and multifaceted ties with the Kazakh diaspora living in foreign countries. At present, diverse and multi-level ties with compatriots, who, due to various historical events, have been scattered around the world, is an important area of Kazakhstan's activity in the international arena.

The Kazakh diaspora, living in countries with a multi-ethnic and multicultural tradition, is fluent in the language of the titular nations, respects their customs and traditions, interacts tolerantly with representatives of various ethnic groups and cultural groups, and at the same time strives to preserve their own national identity and pass it on to their descendants as spiritual wealth of his people.

For our state, which in terms of its area is one of the ten largest countries in the modern world, where on average per 1 sq. km. 7,1 people live in the territory (for example, in Uzbekistan - 73 people), the relevance of this problem is quite obvious.

The paper is analyzed the historical and modern processes of the formation and development of Kazakh diaspora, given their objective and subjective factors, socio-economic, political, cultural and educational features in several historical periods.

During the studying this problem, we have used the following conventional methods:

- Historical analysis (systematic treatment) of the available historical sources and literature, including foreign and Kazakh scientists.

- Interviewing is one of the components of the method of empirical level, based on the developed set of questions via Skype. Having conducted interviewing with the Kazakhs from abroad (Canada, the USA, Germany, the UAE) is studied the basic socio-economic and cultural achievements and problems of the modern Kazakh diaspora [1].

The authoritative Kazakh scientist, the author of numerous works on the history of Kazakh diaspora, Professor G.M. Mendikulova offers six chronologic-thematic stages in the study of this problem [2].

In studying the history of Kazakh diaspora, as a part of Kazakh people we have studied and used works

of domestic and foreign scientists on various aspects of the diaspora as a whole, including the Kazakhs [3].

Scientists consider that in the process of formation and development of Kazakh diaspora can be defined the following steps [4]:

1. The period of the Kazakh-Dzungar war (XVII – mid. of the XVIII centuries).

2. The colonial policy of tsarism and the national and liberation uprising of the Kazakhs against the colonizers in the XIX–early XX centuries.

3. The period of strengthening of the totalitarian regime in the USSR (20-30s of the XX century).

4. The period of immigration to the Western countries and America in the 2nd half of the XX century.

5. The period of the collapse of the Soviet Union, i.e. the years of instability in the first years of sovereignty and following years.

It is also important to note that Kazakh diaspora throughout its history had a violent or forced character of migration, due to political, economic and religious reasons, until the 60s of the XX century, when it began to develop labor immigration to Western Europe, America and Gulf countries.

We consider that Kazakh diaspora living in the far and near abroad is as the cultural heritage keeper of Kazakh people. It has its own explanations for many decades that the Kazakhs living outside of Kazakhstan carefully preserved their traditions, customs and native language. Certain separate compact residence of Kazakh families abroad and practically lack of relations with their historical homeland have allowed them to preserve not only the identity of the culture of the Kazakh people, which for many years of the Soviet regime was subjected to assimilation and filled with many innovations, alien Kazakh culture, language and traditions.

The process of preservation of ethnic identity among Kazakh diaspora has several options: marriage and family, ethnic societies, schools, language and culture. We are talking primarily about the preservation mentality, because while away from historical homeland, many Kazakh diaspora can simply dissolve in the country of residence.

At the present time Kazakh diaspora becomes an important element of the international activity of Kazakhstan.

There is the process of preservation of ethnic and cultural identity among Kazakh diaspora, which develops due to close relations with their historical Homeland – the Republic of Kazakhstan and unifying events, organized by the Embassy of Kazakhstan in the countries of residence of Kazakh diaspora.

The first World Kurultai of the Kazakhs was held 30 years ago on September 29, 1992 (which became a historical date for the fate of Kazakh diaspora). The First President of the Republic of Kazakhstan N.A. Nazarbayev addressed to all Kazakhs living today in more than forty countries return to their homeland - Kazakhstan. The result of the forum was the creation of the World Association of the Kazakhs.

The Kazakhs from Turkey, Germany, France, Russia, Mongolia, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Sweden, Norway and other countries participated in the congress. 750 delegates from 33 countries of the world arrived in Kazakhstan. The main objective of the World Kurultai of the Kazakhs was a cultural reunion of the Kazakhs in the world.

Since then there have been five congresses of the Kazakhs. The Second World Kurultai of the Kazakhs was held in October 2002, in the holy city of Turkestan. There were about 400 Kazakhs from all over the world. The Third World Congress of the Kazakhs took place in September 2005, in Astana. There were representatives of 32 countries. A landmark event in the political life of the country was the Fourth World Kurultai of the Kazakhs, which was held in May 2011. Unlike the other three Kurultais, youth, the leaders of young organizations, student associations from different countries were invited to the fourth Kurultai of the Kazakhs. The representatives of the Kazakh nationality from 35 foreign countries attended this forum. Among the delegates there were the representatives of creative, scientific and pedagogical intelligence, business, sport, government and public organizations and mass media.

The World Kurultai of Kazakhs is held every 5 years. The next 5th Kurultai was held in Nur-Sultan from June 22 to 25, 2017.

At the IV session of the Assembly of Peoples of Kazakhstan of June 6, 1997 the First President of the RK N.A. Nazarbayev in his report "Historical memory, national reconciliation and democratic reform - civil choice" stressed that "Kazakhstan ... all acceptable political and economic means will support the Kazakh diaspora around the world, building relationship of friendship and good neighborliness with the country of residence of the Kazakhs" [5].

For the 30 years of independence, Kazakhstan has pursued a policy of repatriation of ethnic Kazakhs to their historical homeland. The implementation of the repatriation program to the historic homeland of the Kazakhs living abroad, the country in which the share of the titular ethnic group at the time of independence was accounted for over half of the population, started immediately after the collapse of the USSR.

The relocation was carried out on the basis of the 1992 law "On Immigration", according to it the Kazakhs returning to the territory of the Republic in connection with the persecution, oppression, restrictions, rights and freedoms, and also at desire to return to their

historical homeland, it was granted refugee status, but those who left Kazakhstan during the mass repression, persecution, prisoners of war and their descendants - immigrant refugees.

In December 1997, the new law "On migration", the repatriate (kandas) was the "face of the indigenous nationality, exiled from their historical homeland ... due to acts of mass political repressions, illegal requisition of forced collectivization, and other inhumane acts, voluntarily relocated to the Republic of Kazakhstan for permanent residence and also descendants." In accordance with the legislation on the repatriation, the oralmen were eligible for a wide range of benefits, including the provision of housing and cash benefits, but because of the economic difficulties, not all of these benefits have been realized.

For 30 years of independence, it was decided a number of problems: with the transit of border and customs procedures, the citizenship of the output process, training and employment in the new location and etc. The Government of Kazakhstan headed by the President was carried out a large amount of work in the sphere of migration policy. The various laws and regulations were approved by the Migration Policy Programme of 2011 and an action plan for its implementation.

The new law of the RK "On migration", which put into force on August 16, 2011 assumes an increase of the role of foreign enterprises that can assign the status of oralman on site exit.

If we talk about immediate perspectives, the migration authorities of the Republic set as a priority of immigration (repatriation) of ethnic Kazakhs from conflict zones (Tajikistan, Afghanistan), and ecological disaster zones (Uzbekistan, Karakalpakstan).

The fate of the Kazakh diaspora abroad is not ignored by the current leadership of the country. In connection with the change in the military-political situation in Afghanistan, the President of Kazakhstan K.K. Tokayev noted that "Kazakhstan continues to work closely with foreign partners in order to solve current problems. First of all, we organized the evacuation of our compatriots. Now we are considering the possibility of returning representatives of Kazakh diaspora - Kandas from Afghanistan" [6].

According to the authorities and scientists the number of members of Kazakh diaspora is impossible to determine the objective and subjective reasons. According to some data, more than 5 million Kazakhs live outside the territory of Kazakhstan [7].

Unfortunately, the emigration of the Kazakhs, especially Kazakh youth from the country is continues.

Interviewing with Kazakh diaspora once again shows why the Kazakhs, especially young people are leaving Kazakhstan forever. The reasons for leaving abroad are explained as follows:

- Better living conditions (Social benefits, public transport are more efficient and convenient, good healthcare system, safe and friendly neighborhood);
- Freedom of speech;
- Stability and confidence that the foreign government takes care of you and makes all living conditions;

- Higher salaries; [8].

Today, on the one hand, migration is a global phenomenon, on the other hand, the country's leadership should think about the question - why do thousands of promising, talented young people every year leave the country?

We think it is time to create favorable conditions in the republic, and young people will not leave the country forever.

References

1. Interviews with representatives of Kazakh diaspora from the UAE, Germany, the USA, Canada.
2. Mendykulova G. Kazakh diaspora: history and modernity. - Almaty, 2006. S. 45-68 [In Russian].
3. Koblandin K.I., Mendikulova G.M. "History and current development of Kazakhs in Uzbekistan." - Almaty, 2009 [In Kazakh].; Mendykulova G.M. "Historical fate of the Kazakh diaspora. Origin and development. - Almaty, 1997 [In Russian].; Esmagambetova K.L. "A person recognized by the world." - Almaty, 2009 [In Kazakh].; Syroezhkin K.L. Kazakhs in China: essays on socio-economic and cultural development. - Almaty, 1994 [In Russian].; Altai Khalifa. From Homeland to Analope.-Almaty, 1995 [In Kazakh].; Kara A. Mustafa Shokai. Almaty, 2004. [In Kazakh].
4. Mendykulova G.M. Kazakh diaspora: history and modernity. Article. referats.allbest.ru/geography/... [In Russian].
5. N.A. Nazarbayev Historical memory, national harmony and... [In Russian]. e-history.kz/ru/books/library/...
6. Tokaev: We are considering the possibility of returning representatives of the Kazakh diaspora from Afghanistan. www.khabar.kz [In Russian].
7. About Kazakh diaspora. Interview with Gulnara Mendikulova. Damir Sattarov. May 6, 2022 <https://www.caa-network.org/archives/23917/o-kazahskoj-diaspore-intervyu-s-gulnaroj-mendikulovoj>. [In Russian].
8. Interviews with representatives of Kazakh diaspora from the UAE, Germany, the USA, Canada.